

A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON GREEN BANKING CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

The colour green is increasingly being used to denote eco-awareness. Due to this concept, the banking sector is experiencing technological developments, operational improvements, and client behaviour changes. Normal banks, like Green Bank, aim on preserving natural resources and safeguarding the environment while taking into account all social and environmental problems. To promote environmentally friendly practices and lessen the carbon footprint produced by financial activity [2]. Additionally, it is known as the ethical bank and the sustainable bank. Banks should support the innovations, procedures, and goods that considerably reduce their carbon footprint. In terms of increasing paper usage, environmental effects, and energy use (lighting, air conditioning). In today's environmentally conscious society, the adage "Go Green" has acquired popularity and is now relevant to all areas of business [3]. The goal of this study is to examine green banking and point out situations where it has been used.

Keywords: *Green banking, sustainable banking, carbon footprint, energy consumption.*

INTRODUCTION:

As consumer awareness and environmental consciousness rise, businesses cannot survive on revenue alone. They must not ignore the problems that face society and the environment. The environmental preservation movement has made an impact on how businesses are managed. Everyone is becoming more environmentally conscious, whether they are consumers, workers, employers, or members of the general public, as the economy transitions to a "green" one. Organizations are increasingly compelled to use sustainable, environmentally friendly practices. Sustainability is the major issue. Addressing environmental issues is essential in this new era [1].

Like a regular bank, Green Bank considers all social and environmental factors that work to safeguard the environment and conserve natural resources. Lowering the carbon footprint of banking operations and promoting environmentally responsible behaviour are both mentioned. Ethical or sustainable banks are the names given to these companies. Banks and other financial institutions need to put environmental preservation first to fulfil their dual missions. Promoting ethical and socially conscious banking is a bank's first obligation, and its second duty is vital for its commitment to corporate social responsibility [2].

In contrast to typical banks, green banks believe that ethical environmental and social business practices are offered by environmental considerations. They normally weigh all the factors to evaluate whether the project is ecologically advantageous and whether it would have any long-term repercussions before awarding a loan. The loan won't be given unless it conforms to all environmental safety laws. Green banking is promoting environmentally friendly behaviour and reduces the carbon footprint of banking activities [3]

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This comes in many forms;

1. Using online banking instead of branch banking.
2. Paying bills online instead of mailing them.
3. Opening up accounts at online banks, instead of large multi-branch banks.
4. Find the local bank in your area that is taking the biggest steps to support local green initiatives [6].

GREEN BANKING

A group of banking practices known as "green banking" aims to protect the environment and maintain natural resources while taking into account all social and ecological issues.

To preserve natural resources and protect the environment, a range of banking practices collectively referred to as "green banking" must take into account all social and ecological concerns [2].

In that it considers all social and environmental concerns, green banking is also referred to as an ethical bank and is similar to traditional banking. Ethical banking's first focus was on environmental protection. These banks operate like conventional banks in that they work to protect the environment as well as being governed by the same authorities [8].

Benefits and Opportunities of Green Banking

1. As the name implies, green banking reduces unnecessary paperwork, which leads to fewer trees being cut down. To this end, many banks invest in renewable energy and other environmentally friendly programs.
2. E-Statements will be generated as part of G-Banking to update customers' accounts via email as opposed to printing.
3. Many payment services are now freely accessible online, reducing the need for travel and saving money on transportation and gasoline.
4. Green banks frequently offer loans with lower interest rates because they place more emphasis on ecological advantages and other environmentally friendly factors.
5. Customers are urged to manage their accounts online to save time and resources, enhance the transaction experience, and increase productivity. [3]

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Green Banking aims at greener and a clean future. As stated earlier what is needed in the context of this new concept is consumer awareness.

Sharma, Gopal, et al. (2014) examine, with a focus on Mumbai, the extent of consumer knowledge of India's Green Banking plan. Surprisingly, even among those who use the online banking services offered by their banks, over three-quarters of them are not familiar with the term "green banking," according to their primary poll. They discover that the majority of people who are familiar with the term "green banking" associate it with online bill payment and cash deposit systems [20]. Consumers are unaware of other green banking features including green CDs, solar-powered ATMs, and bonds for environmental conservation. Additionally, they make an effort to examine the gender-based variations in bank employees' awareness of green efforts, including E-statements, Net Banking, and green loans. They find that both men and women have the same level of knowledge about green banking using the Chi-Square test for hypothesis testing. According to

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the researchers, technical problems are the biggest barrier to green banking, followed by a lack of education [4].

Nath, Nayak, et al. (2014) Study the World Bank's environmental and social criteria, the RBI's green rating system, and the bank's initiative to implement green practices. They also provide a list of adoption techniques for green banking. Green Coin Rating is another name for the Green Rating Standard. According to this system, the number of recycling operations and carbon emissions is used to evaluate banks. The World Bank has established social and environmental standards for financial institutions. These standards offer solutions to lessen the influence on the environment. Banks must do environmental impact assessments, submit annual reports, and use environmentally friendly technologies. Researchers examine and provide a list of environmental initiatives undertaken by various Indian banks. Indian banks must behave ethically as businesses if they hope to succeed in the global market. [4]

Sudhalakshmi and Chinnadorai (2014) highlight the current situation of Indian banks regarding green banking and note that despite the importance of the "go green" concept for developing nations like India, major efforts have not been made. Banks are supposed to factor in the environment when making loans. Future environmental conditions will improve as a result of every action made now. Thus, India needs a policy change to encourage green banking. Indian banks are lagging in adopting this environmentally friendly trend. In this sense, serious action must be taken [1].

Jha and Bhome (2013) comparable poll as described above to determine and subsequently raise consumer awareness of green banking. By conducting interviews and utilizing specially designed survey questionnaires, they identify specific Green Banking procedures that are required [17]. They recommend several actions, including online banking, green checking accounts (with ATMs and special touch screens), green loans (with low-interest rates for those looking to purchase solar equipment) to support environmentally friendly residential projects, power-saving equipment, and green credit cards, and paper-saving mobile banking. The transition of an organization to sustainability will be ensured by green banking [2].

Yadav and Pathak (2013) learn about the green banking strategies that commercial and public banks have chosen for environmental sustainability. By employing a case study technique, they discover that Indian banks have recognized the significance of acting responsibly toward the environment. In addition, the study's findings show that, except for ICICI Bank, public sector banks have taken more steps than private sector banks. Only ICICI Bank's strategy is a sustainable one in the private sector [5].

OBJECTIVES

- To understand the idea of green banking.
- To ascertain consumer knowledge and awareness levels on green banking.
- To examine the variables influencing the use of green banking
- To know various methods for adopting Green Banking, explore the Prospects for Green Banking, and know the Green Banking challenge.[3]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

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The study was supported by a literature analysis and secondary data. The reports of the Indian Bank, numerous seminars, journals, workshop material, and other pertinent information published on the banks and other websites served as secondary data sources.

Overview of Green Banking

The importance of banks and the need to move sustainably were highlighted by green banking. Green banking usually omits as much of the necessary paperwork as is practicable and depends on online payment processing to offer green cards and green home loans. Additionally, since green loans have lower interest rates than loans from traditional banks, consumers benefit from capital gains [16]. Environmental considerations are given more weight by green banks than conservation accomplishments. The Sustainable Finance Awards were created by the Fiscal Periods and Universal-Investment Establishment, a part of the Biosphere Group Community, to honour companies that do business while taking into account sociological, ecological, and corporate governance challenges [2]

Methods of Green Banking Adoption

Environmental risk management and the search for opportunities for innovative, environmentally conscious products are two aspects of green banking strategy. To assess the risks involved in financing projects to manage environmental risk, banks must adopt acceptable methodologies [19].

(1) Online Savings Account:

Customers of green banking have the option of opening their savings accounts online. Customers can make payments using their accounts and deposit savings with the usage of the internet. Customers have access to electronic bill payment and bank statement delivery. All of these actions will significantly minimize the amount of paper used [1]

(2) Paperless Statements:

Sending bank statements via postal mail is a significant waste of paper. Most banks provide their customers with the opportunity to obtain their financial information automatically through a secure log-in when they authorize online banking [5]. Instead of keeping duplicates of bank documents and accounts in a filing cabinet, a machine might be used to do it.

(3) Practice Straight Credit:

Most business owners will provide employees with the option of receiving their paycheque electronically. This will accelerate the availability of cash and eliminate the need to visit the bank. It also saves time, paper, and a tonne of paperwork [4]

(4) Online Bill Payments:

Customers can pay their invoices online through a safe electronic service, eliminating the need to write and mail cheques [1]. Online bill payments are available for credit card bills, cell phone bills, internet bills, electricity bills, energy bills, and loan repayments. The majority of users of online payments have stopped using checks and exclusively make digital purchases. All of the information and documents can now be stored safely [14].

(5) Debit and credit card Facility:

As a reward, several banks have worked with green organizations like Wildlife Protectors and Sierra Club to develop debit and credit cards [2]. Participating banks will donate a portion of your online banking transaction to charity to help the climate operation.

(6) Electronic Banking:

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The majority of their customers conduct the majority of their banking-related activities online, without physically visiting the bank [2]. Customers need an identification electronic banking and PIN provided by the bank where the individual client maintains an account for this.

(7) Mobile Banking:

A bank offers the mobile banking system as a service. It is convenient to be able to use our handset to pay bills, transfer money, and check the amount. Offering financial transactions through mobile devices is a new channel for financial institutions to broaden their reach. [6]

Based on the data and literature review,

- Bank officials are the primary source of information about green banking.
- Time and cost savings are the least important factors driving the adoption of green banking, whereas convenience is the top reason [18].
- Since they save a significant amount of paperwork and uphold the bank's cleanliness ethic, online banking and ATM services are seen as the first step in implementing green banking. However, the majority of banks continue to offer subpar internet banking services, and the ATM infrastructure is likewise unsatisfactory.
- Green banking encourages financial institutions to use less paper, which improves their reputation. Additionally, it raises knowledge of the environment and environmentally responsible business practices among the stakeholders. However, very few of our institutions have been able to develop such a reputation for green banking. [10]

FINDINGS

- First, operating expenses could be high because providing good services in green banking calls for skilled employees [13]. Qualified employees are required for the strategy's implementation to be successful.
- Because it's a novel concept, it will take some time for buyers to warm up to it.
- It necessitates expensive renewable and recycling technologies;
- Because the buyer needs more practice working with knowledgeable loan officials, their commercial transactions are frequently limited to successful ones. The major barrier to green banking is thought to be the first step [15].
- Environmental audits are required to evaluate the environmental status of a facility, a property, and an operation as well as to identify levels of regulatory compliance, historical and present problems, and any environmental risks and liabilities associated with the project.
- The government must establish and guarantee the enforcement of adequate environmental laws for banks. [8]

SUGGESTIONS

- Spread awareness of green banking among consumers;
- Assist clients in getting media attention.
- A client subscription service that gives benefits to the environment.
- Through the Bank's social responsibility initiatives and increased funding for programs that protect the environment [20].
- The incorporation of sustainability principles requires specific policies that modify the current management practices.
- Write articles about how public transportation is lowering its carbon impact and publish them on a website.

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- Disclose via the Bank's public website and intranet
- Participate in a sport. Encourage green businesses and create outlets [7]

CONCLUSION:

Green banking has benefitted both the expansion of the economy and the enhancement of the environment. Before a few years ago, the majority of traditional banks did not actively pursue investment opportunities in environmentally friendly businesses or industries, nor did they engage in green banking. Indian banks trail their foreign rivals by a wide margin [5]. If Indian banks are to compete on the global stage, they must be conscious of their social and environmental obligations. Along with smaller alternative and cooperative banks, diversified financial service providers, asset management firms, and insurance companies have just recently begun to employ these strategies more regularly [12].

Green Banking has become a buzz word in today's banking world. For going green products, electronic compliances, motor vehicles etc. for eco-friendly atmosphere [11]. Additionally, banks should give priority to financing to economic sectors that have already made notable progress toward being green as well as those that are currently doing so. This concept of "Green Banking" will benefit the economy, businesses, and banks alike. "Green banking" will make it simpler to improve the asset quality of banks in the future in addition to assuring the greening of sectors [2]. For Indian banks, the effective commercialization of "Green Banking" offers both opportunities and challenges. Green banking will act as a potent ex-ante deterrent for the polluting industries who disregard the other institutional regulatory mechanisms if it is implemented honestly. As a result, Indian banks should incorporate green banking into their sustainable banking plan. [9]

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